

Developing the first multi-dimensional measure of access to health-related features for Warsaw, Poland

Michał Iliev^{*1}, James Cheshire^{†1}

¹Department of Geography, UCL

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Summary

The study details the development of the first small area index of accessibility to health-related features for Warsaw, Poland. Inspired by the AHAH Index created for Great Britain, we consider the same indicators, but propose to use multimodal door-to-door travel-time as a measure of accessibility rather than network distances. We find the areas with the poorest access to healthy assets are concentrated in the city centre, with the outskirts having the best access to these. In addition, areas to the west of the river are better connected to health services and retail outlets in contrast to those to the east.

KEYWORDS: health inequality, spatial accessibility, Poland

1. Introduction

Health geographers have long been interested in how accessibility to certain built and physical features might influence one's health and wellbeing. One of the findings around this theme is that people with poorer access to health services (e.g. hospitals) may be less likely to use them (Ensor, 2004). More recently, researchers have begun looking beyond service provision to understand how the location and density of health-negating retail outlets, such as fast-food restaurants, might shape behaviour (Cobb et al., 2015). This complements a long history of research into the impacts of the physical environment on health, particularly in the context of air pollution and access to green areas (Mitchell et al., 2008; White et al., 2013). Understanding the spatial distribution of healthy assets and hazards is therefore crucial for policymakers to effectively account for them.

The index of 'Access to Healthy Assets and Hazards' (AHAH) created for 2016 Great Britain was the first national and open-source multi-dimensional measure of access to health-related features (Green et al., 2018). It is a well-used measure that is replicable in other contexts and so forms the basis to the methodological framework adopted here to create such a measure on a granular scale for Warsaw. We refer to the original, 3 domain, version of the index, since it is the only iteration, which is described in detail in academic papers.

Using open-source data, we calculate 12 variables across three domains and then combine them to form the overall index. The indicators were chosen based on a literature review and only the ones with a clear direction of association with individual health or wellbeing were selected (see Table 1).

* micha.iliev.19@ucl.ac.uk

† james.cheshire@ucl.ac.uk

Table 1 Association of each indicator to health promotion. A positive value (+) means that a value is positively associated with health promotion and vice versa. To help understand the direction of each variable, they were divided into 'low' and 'high' values; for example, a high value for accessibility to bars means that a hexagon is far from one in terms of travel-time, which is health-promoting (+).

Domain	Indicator	Health Promoting	
		Low value	High Value
Health Services	Accessibility to hospitals	+	-
	Accessibility to clinics	+	-
	Accessibility to dentist practices	+	-
	Accessibility to pharmacies	+	-
	Accessibility to sport centres	+	-
Retail Environment	Accessibility to alcohol shops	-	+
	Accessibility to bars	-	+
	Accessibility to fast-food outlets	-	+
Physical Environment	Accessibility to green spaces	-	+
	Nitrogen Dioxide (NO ₂)	+	-
	PM ₁₀ particles	+	-
	Sulphur Dioxide (SO ₂)	+	-

Figure 1 Flow chart depicting the adopted methodology to calculate the individual measures and the AHAH index.

2. Data

The availability of spatial data in Poland is limited and the strength of this study is the creation of a framework that uses open-source datasets from international providers (except air pollution). Compared to the UK, Poland does not have granular (1x1km) air pollution estimates as provided by DEFRA. Instead, the estimates had to be interpolated based on the data from the measuring stations in and around Warsaw. Moreover, no government entity provides accessible data on the location of health services (like NHS) or retail outlets; thus, we had to use POI data provided by the EU SLIPO project.

We originally conducted the study in 2022 and decided to use pre-Covid-19 data to form a model that is not affected by movement restrictions. To calculate travel-time between origin-destination pairs we use the public transport schedule (GTFS) for the weekdays of February 2020 (03.02-07.02). The extracted air quality data are 2019 average values from 12 stations across the city. All other details about the data are presented in Figure 1.

3. Methodology

Aside from the geographical setting, two significant aspects distinguish this study from the original Green et al. (2018) approach (see Fig. 1). The first is the use of a granular hexagonal grid in the place of small area census units, and the second is the use of door-to-door travel-time, which combines walking and public transit as a measure of accessibility.

As Warsaw lacks output areas at a fine granularity (borough level is the smallest), we generate hexagonal cells built upon the H3 indexing system at resolution 9 (area $\approx 97,000 \text{ m}^2$) (Uber Technologies, 2018). Cells whose centroid was further than 100 metres from the closest street network node were excluded, leaving 4712 hexagons at which level all measures were calculated. In contrast, Green et al. (2018) measured each indicator at the postcode level and presented the results at the LSOA level.

Proposing an extension to the original index, we consider multimodal accessibility to Points of Interest (POIs) rather than network (AHAH version 1 and 2) or time-weighted (version 3) distances. This approach considers every stage of a journey between origin and destination, combining the time of walking and public transit journey. Based on a 2015 study, 65% of journeys in Warsaw were either accomplished by only walking or utilising public transportation (Urząd m.st. Warszawy, 2016). Therefore, we consider the multimodal approach to better capture the realistic accessibility to health services or health-negating retail outlets.

We calculate travel-time estimates from the centroid of each hexagon to all POIs and then extract the shortest output for each category. For this purpose, the investigation uses `r5r`, an R package for rapid realistic routing on multimodal transport networks, which requires public transportation schedule data (GTFS) and street network (`pbf`). Due to computational limits and the fact that it is an exploratory project, we calculate travel-times for only a single 10-minute time-window (7:30 – 7:40 AM, beginning of the peak hour). For each origin-destination pair, the engine calculates travel-time for each minute within the time window and the output is the median value. Since the levels of public transport service fluctuate throughout the day (Stepniak et al., 2019), in a future study we plan to consider how this is reflected in temporal differences.

4. Results

Table 2 presents the summary results of each measure. On average, a hexagon is located nearest to a fast-food outlet in comparison to all the other services or outlets measured. Other health-negating retail outlets are less accessible, with alcohol shops and bars being the 3rd and 2nd least accessible POI respectively (out of 8). Average travel-time to health services is good with pharmacies, clinics and sport centres having the best results. Hospitals, on average, are located the furthest away, reflecting their

lower prevalence compared to other categories (73 hospitals vs 864 fast food outlets). The median area of green spaces within a hexagon equals 33,483 m² (approximately a third of hexagon's area). Due to the relatively small number of air quality measurement stations, the results are broadly similar, with all hexagons displaying bad air quality. This aspect can be improved once better air quality data is available.

Table 2 Summary results of each indicator per hexagon (N=4712)

Domain	Indicator	Median value	Interquartile range
Retail Environment	Accessibility to Fast-Food Outlets (min)	15	9–25
	Accessibility to Alcohol shops (min)	21	12–31
	Accessibility to Bars (min)	23	14–34
Health Services	Accessibility to Hospitals (min)	30	21–41
	Accessibility to Pharmacies (min)	16	9–25
	Accessibility to Clinics (min)	18	10–27
	Accessibility to Dentist Practices (min)	20	12–29
	Accessibility to Sport Centres (min)	18	12–28
Physical Environment	Passive accessibility to green spaces (m ²)	33,487	12,399–64,478
	Nitrogen Dioxide (µg m ⁻³)	25.89	24.34–28.66
	Sulphur Dioxide (µg m ⁻³)	2.71	2.53–2.98
	Particulate Matter 10 (µg m ⁻³)	27.67	26.04–28.56

Figure 2 Visualisation of the three domains of the AHAAH index in Warsaw. (a) Health Service domain, (b) Retail Environment Domain, and (c) Physical Environment Domain

Figure 3 Overall Index of Access to Healthy Assets and Hazards in Warsaw.

As Figure 2 shows, the Health Service Domain (a) demonstrates better accessibility to health services for central areas, and regions west of the Vistula River. The Retail Environment Domain (b) displays a very similar pattern, with central areas having higher accessibility to health-negating retail outlets. Since the direction of the relationship with health promotion is reversed for the retail domain, the map displays opposite colours. The same pattern of the two domains suggests that they capture similar processes (e.g. public transport provision) and that areas which have good access to health services have also good access to health-negating retail outlets. The Physical Environment Domain (c) displays a different pattern, with central and eastern areas having the worst results.

Figure 3 presents the overall AHAH Index. Although central areas were among the best performing areas in Health Service Domain, they are within the unhealthiest group in the overall index. The other clusters of bad performing hexagons are in Włochy (South-West), Rembertów (East) and Wawer (South-East) districts. The best performing hexagons are mainly located near the city borders in the Białołęka (North), Ursus (West) and Ursynów (South) districts.

5. Discussion

This paper details the first study that simultaneously considered access to multiple features of built and physical environments in Warsaw to assess the ‘healthiness’ of its geographical areas. Furthermore, it proposes integrating multimodal accessibility measures into such composite indicators.

A notable strength of composite indicators, such as the one considered in this research, lies in their ease of interpretation and capacity to serve as a powerful tool of communication. However, as with every index, the AHAH is subject to various constraints related to data and conceptual challenges (see Daras et al., 2019). The index is based on the ranking of hexagons; thus, the results are only a relative measure of ‘healthiness’ and they cannot be considered outside the context of this study. Moreover, due to the unavailability of granular socio-demographic data, we could not test whether the index is a good predictor of individual-level health in Warsaw. Finally, as mentioned before, we did not consider temporal differences in accessibility via public transportation which may significantly change the results (Tenkanen et al., 2016).

Moving forward, we aim to gain further insight into the realities of accessibility to health-related features across Warsaw. Particularly, we want to integrate temporality (i.e. measuring travel-time at different times) and different modes of transportation (e.g. car vs public transit) into our model.

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Biographies

Michał Iliev is a first year PhD student in Human Geography at University College London. His current research concerns the application of mobile phone location data to infer activity-based mobility patterns in London.

James Cheshire is Professor of Geographic Information and Cartography at UCL, Director of the UCL Social Data Institute and Deputy Director of the ESRC Consumer Data Research Centre